

I-CLAIM

Improving the Living
and Labour Conditions
of Irregularised Migrant
Households in Europe

Racial Logics of Irregular Migration in Europe

Policy, Perception, and Precarity

Stefano Piemontese
Nando Sigona
Laurence Lessard-Phillips
Emmanuel Achiri

February 2026

Funded by
the European Union

UK Research
and Innovation

Funded by the European Union under Grant Number 101094373. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency or UK Research and Innovation. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Executive Summary

This report examines how race and racism shape the production, governance, and lived experience of migrants' irregularity across Europe. Drawing on comparative research in Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom, it analyses how racial logics operate within migration, labour, and welfare systems, and in the narratives and perceptions that sustain them. The study forms part of the Horizon Europe and UKRI-funded Improving the Living and Labour Conditions of Irregularised Migrant Households in Europe (I-CLAIM) project.

Across these contexts, racism does not merely operate beneath the surface of law and policy: it structures how access to rights, belonging, and worth are organised. The report conceptualises racism as systemic: not as a set of individual prejudices, but as a structural logic embedded in legal frameworks, bureaucratic routines, everyday governance, as well as the daily practices and lived experiences of migrants. Visa systems, sponsorship mechanisms, welfare conditionality, and structural exclusion reproduce racial hierarchies despite formal commitments to equality. Bureaucratic discretion weaponise administrative procedures into mechanisms of control, while labour regimes transform dependency into economic value. These processes collectively reproduce a racialised governance of mobility.

The analysis spans three interconnected domains. First, legal and policy infrastructures reveal how race operates through nationality, origin, and perceived cultural or religious proximity to shape access to rights and residence. Second, political, media, and civil society narratives show how moral hierarchies of deservingness—often framed through religion, culture, or gender—legitimise exclusionary and racist policies. Third, comparative evidence from agriculture, domestic work, and food delivery demonstrates how race, gender, and status intersect in structuring recruitment, segmentation, and exploitation. In all sectors, irregularity functions as a tool of racialised labour division and discipline that renders certain groups permanently disposable.

Importantly, the report highlights that racialisation extends beyond non-EU or irregularised migrants. Racialised EU minorities—such as Roma people—are often migrantised and governed with the same control logics as those deemed 'irregular', facing racism, intensified surveillance, spatial exclusion, and restricted access to welfare and work. Their experiences demonstrate how racism produces irregularity, collapsing the distinction between nationality, administrative status and de facto exclusion.

Across Europe, irregularity emerges as both a product and an organising principle of racial order. Racialisation legitimises inequality, while migration policies provide the institutional machinery that sustains it. Recognising racism as the driving force of irregularity is essential to understanding and addressing migrant precarity. Confronting irregular migration in Europe therefore requires engaging with the racialised foundations of its border, labour, and welfare regimes.

Despite its commitment to tackling structural racism, the new EU Anti-Racism Strategy 2026–2030 stops short of interrogating migration governance as a racialising infrastructure. While its emphasis on xenophobia and anti-immigrant sentiment is welcome, the absence of explicit recognition and mechanisms of accountability risks obscuring how immigration law, residence regimes, labour market controls, and welfare—enforcement linkages systematically produce and reproduce racial hierarchies. The findings of this report substantiate this gap: across countries and labour sectors, racialised inequalities are not only experienced as prejudice or exclusion but are actively produced through legal status differentiation,

employer-tied permits, bureaucratic discretion and delay, delegated enforcement, and conditional access to social rights—revealing migration governance itself as a central mechanism of racial differentiation.

How to cite:

Piemontese, S., Sigona, N., Lessard-Phillips, L., Achiri, E. (2026). *Racial Logics of Irregular Migration in Europe: Policy, Perception, and Precarity*. I-CLAIM.

Table of Contents

Executive Summary	2
Preface: The Other Side of the Story	5
1. Introduction	6
2. Methodological note	7
3. Racialised legal and policy infrastructures	7
3.1. Bureaucratic Practices and the Racialisation of Administration	9
3.2. Institutional and Systemic Racism in Migration Governance	9
3.3. Anti-Discrimination Frameworks and Counter-Initiatives	10
3.4. Systemic Racism as Infrastructure	11
4. Race in the Narrative Construction of Irregular Migrants	11
4.1. Media Representations: Gendered Racialisation, Bureaucratic Labelling, and Racialised Silencing ...	11
4.2. Political Discourses: Stratifying Deservingness Through Racialisation	13
4.3. The Civil Society Dilemma: Making Race Visible or Invisible?	14
4.4. Racialisation without Race: Proxy Mechanisms in European Migration Narratives.....	15
4.5. Cross-cutting Themes	16
5. Race and Racialisation in Public Perceptions of Irregular Migrants	16
5.1. Hiring Preferences and Perceptions of Integration	17
Hiring preferences	17
Assessing integration	18
6. Racial Discrimination and Racialised Segmentation in Migrant Work	19
6.1. Agriculture	20
6.2. Domestic Work	21
6.3. Food Delivery	23
6.4. Cross-sectoral analysis	25
7. Conclusions	25
8. References	27

Preface: The Other Side of the Story

Emmanuel Achiri, ENAR

I grew up in a society in Africa where the dream for many was to travel to and work in Europe. Our history books—products of French and British colonialism—and our TV channels, dominated by Canal+, spoon-fed us a carefully curated vision of Europe as a just society, where everyone, irrespective of race, faith, national origin, gender, or social status, was supposedly equal.

Yet at 14, I stumbled upon *Das Kapital* and *The Wretched of the Earth* on my economics teacher's desk. Being a consummate reader himself, he allowed me to borrow them. From then on, it became difficult to reconcile what I watched on TV and read in those history books with the anti-racist and class lens through which I instinctively viewed the world—even though, at that age, I did not fully grasp the depth of these analyses. What I felt, rather, was a growing weariness toward the mainstream depictions of European society: one where equality triumphs and the legal and policy infrastructures are imagined as inherently designed to deliver fairness and justice for all.

A couple of years later, I moved first to Europe's border and then into Europe. My life trajectory—shaped by a combination of different factors—led me to work specifically on the nexus of mobility and policing, perhaps two of the policy areas where the narrative of Europe as a just society most visibly collapses under scrutiny. Working in these fields, I am constantly confronted with the reality of two Europes: one for white Europeans, where the legal and policy infrastructure, at least in its idealised form, is oriented toward justice, equality, and fairness; and another for racialised Europeans and racialised migrants, where the same system is configured to produce a second-tier group who are easily exploitable, discardable, and excludable. In this sense, my history books and the TV in our living room did not exactly lie; they simply obscured the other half of the story. One could say Europe is indeed a just society—just not for those it refuses to be fair towards.

This report, *Racial Logics of Irregular Migration in Europe: Policy, Perception, and Precarity*, does an excellent job of peering beneath the façade of a just and fair Europe to illustrate how race, racism, and racialisation shape the production, governance, and lived experience of migrants' irregularity across Europe. Drawing on research conducted over two years across various European countries, the report dissects the racial logics that underpin the irregularisation of migration and the experiences of irregularised migrants. It demonstrates how racism is embedded not only in legal and policy infrastructures but also in the narratives and perceptions surrounding migrants, and how racial segmentation and discrimination operate across labour sectors such as agriculture, domestic work, and delivery work throughout Europe.

This report is not essential reading for migrants themselves, as their bodies and minds already bear the record of this racial violence. Yet it is crucially relevant for policymakers, academics, civil society actors, and other stakeholders engaged in migration governance in Europe. By applying a race lens to labour, migration, and irregularity, it convincingly reveals the underbelly of the precarity imposed on racialised migrants and certain racial minorities in Europe.

In today's Europe, where politicians across the political spectrum—from the Left to the Right—constantly debate how to control “irregular migration”, this report makes clear that the problem does not lie with those who have been racialised, irregularised, and exploited, but with the racist legal and political infrastructures, and the narratives and perceptions that both create and sustain them.

1. Introduction

This report investigates the racial logics underpinning the irregularisation of migration and the experiences of irregular migrants in Europe, focusing on how racism—both explicit and implicit—structures the production, governance, and lived experience of irregularity. It contributes to the Horizon Europe and UKRI-funded I-CLAIM project, which examines how irregularity is produced through the interaction of migration, labour, and welfare regimes. While the language of “race” is often absent from European policy, the management of migration remains deeply racialised. Administrative categories such as *illegal*, *extracomunitario*, *sans papiers*, or *undocumented* carry the weight of colonial histories and hierarchies that continue to shape Europe’s social and political imagination.

The report draws on comparative research in Finland, Germany, Italy, the Netherlands, Poland, and the United Kingdom, integrating analyses of law, policy, public discourse, perception surveys, and sectoral ethnographies. It treats racism as a logic of organisation, woven into the procedures, classifications, and institutions that determine whose mobility is facilitated, whose is restricted, and under what conditions belonging becomes conditional or revocable.

The analysis first explores legal and policy infrastructures, showing how the persistent exclusion of immigration status and migration governance from equality frameworks—including, surprisingly, the recently approved EU Anti-Racism Strategy (2026–2030)—together with visa sponsorship dependency and the fusion of welfare provision with control measures, reproduces racialised hierarchies through law and bureaucracy. It then examines narratives and perceptions, analysing how political, media, and civil-society discourses construct irregular migration through proxies such as nationality, religion, gender, and behaviour, producing moral hierarchies of deservingness that shape policy and opinion. Finally, it focuses on labour markets, where the racialisation of work and immigration status sustains systems of dependency, informality, and control across agriculture, domestic work, and food delivery.

The report also shows that racialisation is not confined to non-EU or irregularised migrants. Racialised EU minorities—such as Roma people—often experience forms of exclusion, surveillance, and precarity strikingly similar to those faced by migrants with insecure or irregular status. Their treatment as internal foreigners reveals how the logic of irregularity extends beyond residence status and into the social production of difference within the European Union itself.

By connecting these domains, the report demonstrates that the governance of irregular migration in Europe cannot be understood apart from its racialised underpinnings. Racism is not a residual or historical phenomenon but a structural feature of how Europe regulates mobility, labour, and belonging—operating through both national origin and embodied markers such as being read as Black or Brown. The persistence of irregularity is thus a symptom of a broader racial order that defines who counts as European—and who remains perpetually on probation within it.

2. Methodological note

This report is based on a comparative analysis of research conducted over a two-year period (September 2023–August 2025) across six European countries as well as at the level of EU institutions. The research is structured around four main analytical streams: policy frameworks, political and media narratives, public attitudes, and lived experiences of irregularised migrants within specific labour market sectors.

While some data sources are longitudinal, such as the policy analysis spanning two decades (2005–2025) and the narrative analysis covering five years (2019–2023), others are more temporally bounded, reflecting fieldwork activities carried out over several months but nonetheless capturing the sedimentation of stories and understandings of irregularity over time. Together, these diverse strands offer a comprehensive and multi-layered view of the politics and realities of irregular migration in Europe, and the way race emerges, operates and shapes the governance, representation, and experiences of irregular migrants in Europe.

The policy analysis draws on 65 expert interviews in the six European countries, alongside a mapping of legislative and normative changes over the past two decades. The impact of major geopolitical events such as Brexit, the Covid-19 pandemic, and the war in Ukraine, which have significantly influenced the politics of irregularity across Europe. The narrative analysis is based on a five-year corpus (2019–2023) of 40,683 texts comprising over 125 million words in total, including media articles, parliamentary debates, ministerial speeches, party manifestos, and third-sector publications. This corpus traces how race and irregularity are constructed in public discourse (see Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025b). Public attitudes were examined through a survey conducted by YouGov in February 2025, involving 6,322 respondents, representative of the adult population in each I-CLAIM country. Finally, the analysis of migrant experience draws on ethnographic research based on 244 in-depth interviews and observations conducted between summer 2024 and spring 2025 with migrant workers in three key sectors: agriculture, domestic work, and food delivery. Complementary interviews with employers, legal professionals, NGO staff, and trade union representatives were also conducted as part of this ethnographic work. This component captures the everyday realities of racialised labour segmentation and the structural production of dependency and exclusion among racially minoritised migrants.

3. Racialised legal and policy infrastructures

Racism and ethnic discrimination are embedded in the legal, policy, and bureaucratic infrastructures that govern migration in Europe. Racist logics are not external to migration governance but are integral to its design and operation, shaping how laws are written, policies are implemented, and bureaucratic procedures are carried out.

Across the six national contexts, formal commitments to equality coexist with systems that reproduce racialised differentiation through law, policy, and administration (Hajer et al., 2024; Matuszczyk et al., 2024; Merikoski et al., 2024; Palumbo & Marchetti, 2024; Piemontese & Sigona, 2024; Rheindorf et al., 2024). Irregularity itself emerges as a relational position within these systems—an outcome of how states classify, manage, and discipline mobility. The infrastructures of irregularity are therefore also infrastructures of race, shaping who can enter, remain, and belong within Europe (Sigona & van Liempt, 2025).

At the European level (Carrera & Colombi, 2025), the legal foundations of equality policies are defined by the Racial Equality Directive (2000/43/EC) and the Employment Equality Directive (2000/78/EC). These instruments prohibit discrimination on the grounds of racial or ethnic origin, yet they explicitly exclude nationality and immigration status from their scope. This exclusion is not an oversight but a structural boundary that separates the domain of migration governance from that of equality protection. As a result, the very field in which racialisation is most pervasive—the governance of entry, residence, and work—remains legally exempt from anti-discrimination scrutiny.

Nationally, our research points to a consistent pattern of stratified legality. Immigration and residence laws establish hierarchies of entitlement that map onto racial and geographic lines: EU citizens at the top, long-term residents in the middle, and temporary or undocumented migrants at the bottom. Criteria such as income thresholds, sponsorship requirements, “safe countries” and “integration” tests appear neutral but have systematically unequal effects. They reproduce racial hierarchies by aligning legal privilege with alleged European origin, whiteness, and socioeconomic advantage.

Across the six countries, migration and labour regulation are deeply intertwined. Work permits are frequently tied to individual employers, and visa renewals depend on uninterrupted employment. The coupling of residence rights and labour market participation transforms administrative status into an instrument of economic discipline. Those who are racialised as “other”—Black African, South Asian and Southeast Asian migrants, as well as people from the Middle East and North Africa—often occupy the lowest rungs of this hierarchy, where dependency on employers and intermediaries curtails the capacity to claim rights or change jobs.

Conditionality extends beyond employment to welfare and social protection. In many national systems, access to healthcare, housing, and benefits depends on residence status, while in others, public officials have reporting duties toward immigration authorities. This fusion of welfare and control embeds bordering practices within everyday administration. It also produces a moral economy in which racially minoritised migrants are publicly portrayed as burdens or threats to social cohesion, legitimising their exclusion through practices and policies that render them “irregular”.

Together, these legal and policy features form what we call Europe’s “infrastructure of irregularity” (Näre et al., 2024; Sigona & van Liempt, 2025): a regulatory order that formally condemns racism yet continually reproduces racialised inequality through its internal logic of differentiation. In the following sections, we will explore the building blocks of this infrastructure, which develop across specific bureaucratic practices and institutional-political rationalities, while also examining the emergence of counter-initiatives that challenge the status quo.

3.1. Bureaucratic Practices and the Racialisation of Administration

If laws set the parameters of inclusion and exclusion, bureaucracy enacts them in practice. As our research shows, the racialisation of migration governance operates not primarily through explicit prejudice but through routine administrative procedures—how applications are processed, how discretion is exercised, and how time is managed.

Discretion is central to this process. Caseworkers, police, and consular officials interpret open-ended categories such as “credibility”, “good character”, or “sufficient means”. These judgments are shaped by racialised assumptions about reliability, honesty, and deservingness, transforming social stereotypes into administrative outcomes. Bureaucracy thus translates cultural hierarchies developed and reinforced during colonisation into material effects.

Administrative delay represents another key mechanism. Long waiting periods for residence permits, visa renewals, or regularisation convert temporariness into ‘irregularity’. Bureaucratic time becomes a means of control, producing uncertainty that restricts movement and employment. Such delays are often systemic rather than accidental, reflecting under-resourced offices and political ambivalence toward migrant inclusion.

Delegated enforcement further extends these dynamics into the fabric of daily life. Employers, housing providers, healthcare officials, and banks are tasked with verifying immigration status, multiplying the points at which migrants can be excluded or reported. This diffusion of control, which reflects a broader outsourcing of border enforcement to private actors, normalises suspicion and embeds racialised profiling and surveillance within ordinary interactions, affecting not only irregular migrants but also racialised citizens and residents.

Even humanitarian and municipal responses frequently reproduce the same logic of conditionality. Access to support programmes is typically mediated by eligibility criteria, reporting requirements, and funding cycles that render assistance temporary and discretionary. Bureaucratic compassion softens but does not transform the underlying system; it confirms migrants’ dependence rather than asserting their rights.

In these ways—through discretion, delay, delegation, and conditional care—bureaucracy operates not as a neutral or technical apparatus but as a racialising infrastructure. Its procedures and routines, often framed as impartial and objective, are not the antithesis of racism but one of its institutional forms.

3.2. Institutional and Systemic Racism in Migration Governance

Across national and local administrations, our research identifies systemic racism as a defining feature of migration governance. This form of racism does not rely on overt hostility or discriminatory intent; it arises from institutional design and political rationalities that treat migration as a matter of security, control, and risk management.

Racialised categorisation is a pervasive mechanism. Administrative labels such as “high-skilled”, “essential”, “temporary”, “seasonal”, “asylum seeker”, or “irregular” are framed as neutral descriptors, yet they carry implicit assumptions about productivity, compliance, and threat that are deeply racialised. These classifications—as we will see later, heavily deployed in public narratives on irregular migration due to their evocative power—establish hierarchies of worth that map closely onto global racial orders, legitimising differentiated treatment within the bounds of legality.

Spatialised control constitutes another expression of systemic racism. Bordering is not confined to frontiers but extends through internal policing, workplace inspections, and data sharing between agencies. Public space becomes racialised terrain where those marked by visible difference, accent or other racialised phenotypes are more likely to be questioned, stopped, or denied access to services.

Finally, the intersection of race and status produces cumulative disadvantage. Temporary and employer-linked permits make racialised groups particularly vulnerable to losing regular residence statuses. Bureaucratic errors, changing regulations, or employer misconduct can instantly precipitate irregularity, locking individuals into cycles of dependency that reflect and reinforce racial hierarchies.

Across contexts, these mechanisms converge to form a racialised governance apparatus: one that manages populations through differentiated legality rather than through explicit racial exclusion.

3.3. Anti-Discrimination Frameworks and Counter-Initiatives

Despite these entrenched structures, our research identifies a range of initiatives—some institutional, others, grassroots—that attempt to challenge racialised exclusion. At EU level, the Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020–2025¹ marked an important rhetorical shift by recognising structural racism as a policy concern and by promoting national action plans, improved data collection, and engagement with racialised communities. This orientation is carried forward in the Anti-Racism Strategy 2026–2030,² which further consolidates the language of structural racism and intersectionality and commits to mainstreaming anti-racism across EU policy domains. However, both the Action Plan and the new Strategy engage migration primarily through the lens of xenophobia, anti-migrant sentiment, and social inclusion, while leaving largely unexamined the role of immigration law and governance as sites where racialised hierarchies are institutionally produced. As a result, migration governance remains at the margins of EU anti-racism policy. Other EU instruments, such as the proposed Platform Work Directive, the Single Permit Directive, and the Corporate Sustainability Due Diligence Directive, may strengthen protections for migrant workers in precarious sectors, but they similarly stop short of addressing the racialised foundations of migration law itself.

Within member states, fragmented but significant efforts have emerged. Some municipalities have introduced “firewalls” between public services and immigration enforcement to guarantee access to healthcare, police protection or education without fear of denunciation. Others have embedded intercultural mediators within labour inspection or welfare services to facilitate communication and trust. Equality bodies and ombudsmen investigate cases of racial profiling or discriminatory treatment, though their mandates rarely extend to irregular migrants. Across the countries considered for this study, civil society organisations provide legal aid, shelters, and information campaigns that extend a measure of protection beyond formal rights frameworks, yet their sustainability depends on local funding and political support.

These initiatives show that anti-racist practice can emerge even within restrictive systems, but their impact remains limited. They tend to alleviate the most visible harms of racialised governance rather than dismantle its structural causes.

¹ A Union of Equality: EU Anti-Racism Action Plan 2020–2025, European Commission, COM(2020) 565 final (2020).

² Union of Equality: Anti-Racism Strategy 2026–2030, European Commission, COM(2026) 12 final (2026).

3.4. Systemic Racism as Infrastructure

The comparative evidence demonstrates that racism within European migration governance is not episodic but infrastructural. Legal frameworks define hierarchies of belonging; bureaucracies enforce them through discretion and delay; and welfare and labour systems stabilise them through conditionality and dependence. Together, they create a regime in which irregularity is racialised by design.

Anti-discrimination law and policy articulate important commitments to equality, yet they remain incomplete in their reach, often failing to protect the very populations most affected by racialised governance, such as migrants. The contradiction between the promise of universal rights and their selective application is not merely a matter of poor implementation but a product of the system's architecture. Bureaucratic routines and legal categories, while formally neutral, achieve what overt racism no longer claims: the continuous differentiation of populations according to perceived origin, utility, and worth.

Understanding racism as infrastructural is essential to grasp how migrant irregularity is constructed in Europe. As the following sections of the report will explore, racialised structures—though often operating behind the scenes—actively shape imaginaries, logics and interpretations that circulate through public narratives, influence public perceptions and in the end serve to justify political initiatives, revealing how systemic racism forms both the foundation and connective tissue of Europe's irregularity regime.

4. Race in the Narrative Construction of Irregular Migrants

Public discourse surrounding irregular migration is deeply shaped by racialisation processes. While explicit references to race are often absent, racialised logics permeate media, political, and civil society narratives through proxies such as national origin, religion, gender, and behavioural stereotypes. These discursive mechanisms construct irregular migrants not merely as legal subjects but as racialised figures whose perceived cultural proximity, economic utility, and moral worth determine whether they are seen as socially and economically desirable or undesirable, deserving or undeserving of compassion and protection.

In the following sections, we will analyse how race is used as an evocative device to construct migrant irregularity in narratives about migrant irregularity across media, political debates, and civil society in the six countries studied (see Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025a for a comparative discussion of narratives). We will explore the main trends within each of these three domains and the peculiarities of each country. We will then pay particular attention to how different proxies and replacements of race are used within different narrative ecosystems, shaped by different ways in which migrant-produced diversity is interpreted.

4.1. Media Representations: Gendered Racialisation, Bureaucratic Labelling, and Racialised Silencing

Across European media landscapes, representations of irregular migrants are deeply racialised, yet they operate through the intersectional use of proxy categories, among which gender plays a central role. Masculinity is frequently linked to specific ethno-racial and religious markers, such as Sub-Saharan, North African, Middle Eastern origin, and affiliation with Islam. This racialised masculine figure becomes symbolic of danger to national security, social cohesion, and cultural identity, fuelling securitarian, racist, and xenophobic rhetoric.

This construction is reinforced by seemingly neutral administrative categories such as *illegal* in the United Kingdom, *veiligelander* in the Netherlands, or *extracomunitario* in Italy. Beneath their apparent neutrality, these labels carry strong derogatory and racialising undertones, evoking entrenched images of threatening Black, Brown, Muslim, or broadly “non-European” migrants. They stigmatise migrants while functioning as rhetorical devices that legitimise exclusionary migration and asylum policies.

Another recurring thread in European media narratives is the dehumanisation of migrants, which occurs either through the vulnerabilisation, particularly of women, portrayed as passive victims of trafficking in British narratives, or through their depiction as faceless, depersonalised masses across most national contexts, or weaponised subjects in geopolitical conflicts in Polish and Finnish narratives. These patterns vary across places but share a logic of “racialised silencing” and erasure of migrant agency. In all these instances, the migrant is reduced to a body to be managed, contained, or repelled.

In the United Kingdom, media portray irregular migrants as morally suspect and criminalised, often in relation to maritime border crossings and framed through binaries of “legality” and “illegality”. Gendered and racialised stereotypes intersect: men are depicted as Black, Muslim, Pakistani, or Albanian and associated with criminality and threat, while women are portrayed as Muslim, Asian, Latin American, or Roma, often in contexts of trafficking or reproductive vulnerability. Racialisation is further reinforced through dehumanising language, such as migrants being *transported*, *sent*, or *packed*, which strips them of agency and reduces them to objects within deportation logistics (Piemontese, 2025).

Media in the Netherlands racialise irregular migrants through the figure of the *veiligelander*, an apparently neutral term referring to asylum seekers from so-called “safe countries”, typically North African states such as Morocco and Algeria. These individuals are portrayed as culturally incompatible and morally undeserving for protection, linked to petty crime, public nuisance, and manipulation of European asylum systems (Hajer, 2024).

In Germany, irregular migrants are constructed as an undifferentiated mass, racialised primarily through religious markers. The archetype of the “young Muslim man” dominates media portrayals, depicted as criminal, culturally incompatible, and resistant to integration (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025c). Lexical choices such as *influx*, *more*, *many*, and *arrival* contribute to the dehumanisation of migrants, reducing them to quantifiable threats (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025c).

Poland presents a media discourse that is dominated by a securitarian framing, especially in relation to the Polish-Belarusian border crisis. Migrants, primarily male, from the Middle East and Africa are depicted as faceless masses, *pushed* by hostile regimes, and described using terms such as *wave*, *mass*, and *inflow*, which strip them of individuality and reinforce their construction as geopolitical threats (Homel-Ficenes & Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025).

In Finland, media narratives are also shaped by geopolitical anxieties and racialised perceptions of threat. Ukrainian refugees are depicted as war victims welcomed into Finnish homes and granted municipal rights. In contrast, asylum seekers from Afghanistan and African countries are portrayed as *illegal* border crossers, with emphasis on their masculinity and presumed danger. Echoing Polish media, they are also framed as instruments of hybrid warfare (Merikoski, 2025).

Media in Italy, while less explicit in racial discourse, rely on national and occupational markers to racialise migrants. Male migrants from Africa, India, and Romania are depicted both as exploited agricultural

labourers and as sources of criminality and public disorder. The term *extracomunitario* (non-EU citizen), like the Dutch *veiligelander*, operates as a racialised category. Meanwhile, female migrant caregivers are rendered invisible, with minimal reference to their national origins (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025).

4.2. Political Discourses: Stratifying Deservingness Through Racialisation

Political discourse across the six countries closely mirrors and reinforces media representations of irregular migration, particularly through racialised and gendered framings. These narratives do not merely reflect political debate; they actively shape policy by operationalising media-produced images into criteria for inclusion, exclusion, and resource allocation. Gendered racialisation in the UK, the problematisation of North African or Muslim men in the Netherlands and Germany, the weaponisation of migration in Finland and Poland, and the focus on labour and exploitation in Italy are recurring threads that connect political and media debates.

Narratives tend to adopt a legalistic and technocratic tone, which masks the underlying racialised logics that structure migration governance. Through this language, migrants are categorised into hierarchies of deservingness and desirability, based on perceived cultural proximity, economic utility, and moral worth. These hierarchies are often racialised, with religious and national markers serving as proxies for race. A consistent pattern emerges across Dutch, German, Polish, and Finnish debates: the juxtaposition of the undeserving racially minoritised irregular migrant with the deserving Ukrainian refugee, who is framed as culturally proximate, brave, and economically valuable. Against this backdrop, while mainstream political discourse tends to obscure racialisation through bureaucratic language, far-right parties across these countries frequently make overtly racist or evocative statements.

In the United Kingdom, political narratives distinguish between desirable and undesirable migrants based on economic productivity and moral worth. Racialisation operates subtly, often through gendered stereotypes rather than explicit racial categories. Women from culturally proximate Eastern European countries are portrayed as innocent and in need of protection, while men from Sub-Saharan Africa and the Balkans are depicted as threatening and socially disengaged due to their youth and single status. These framings echo media portrayals and inform policy decisions around detention, deportation, and welfare support (Piemontese, 2025).

In the Netherlands, political discourse mirrors media portrayals of *veiligelancers*, which are framed as morally undeserving and culturally incompatible. Parliamentary debates often centre on the racialised figure of the *veiligelancers* to justify austere shelter regimes. In contrast, Ukrainian refugees are described in more humane terms and linked to decentralised, community-based accommodation (Hajer, 2024).

Germany similarly employs racialised and gendered tropes in political discourse that question the cultural and economic compatibility of migrants and imply their inferiority. The archetype of the “young Muslim man” is constructed as criminal and culturally incompatible, while female Ukrainian refugees are vulnerabilised and framed as vulnerable and deserving. Islam is portrayed as a threat to social cohesion, linked to religious radicalisation and political instability (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025c).

In Poland, political narratives are dominated by the language of hybrid warfare, particularly in relation to the Polish-Belarusian border. Migrants from the Middle East and Africa are framed as *threat* and *aggressors*, though typically depicted as passive instruments *manipulated* by the Belarusian regime. By contrast,

Ukrainians are consistently represented as refugees and as the migrant group most closely associated with work. Religious categories, especially Muslim, are used to homogenise and exclude, reinforcing a racialised boundary between *us* (Poles/Europeans) and *them* (non-European others). Far-right rhetoric often invokes national symbols and colours—white and red—to entrench this dichotomy (Homel-Ficenes & Grzymała-Każłowska, 2025).

In Italy, political discourse avoids explicit race-talk but relies heavily on administrative and para-administrative categories with racialised undertones. Migration debates focus on labour exploitation and trafficking, often adopting an ostensibly empathetic stance while advocating for repatriation. This duality reveals how vulnerability is constructed and deployed instrumentally, particularly in relation to Black and Indian agricultural labourers (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025).

Finland presents a more neutral tone in mainstream political discourse, but the presence of the xenophobic party The Finns in government since 2023 has introduced overtly racist commentaries. These evoke colonial tropes and racialised fear, casting migrants as deceptive and threatening. Political discussions often implicitly racialise migrants by contrasting the deserving Ukrainian refugee with undeserving migrants and asylum seekers entering Europe irregularly via Libya, the Middle East, Russia and Belarus, who are described as a threatening flood to be managed or tools of hybrid warfare (Merikoski, 2025).

4.3. The Civil Society Dilemma: Making Race Visible or Invisible?

Across six European countries, civil society actors consistently offer more critical, inclusive, and humanising narratives on migration compared to dominant political and media discourses. These organisations often foreground “lived experiences”, challenge racialised representations, and highlight structural inequalities. While approaches vary by national context, common themes include critiques of racialisation, emphasis on migrant agency, and attention to institutional violence and human rights.

In several cases, the racialisation embedded in public narratives is explicitly addressed and challenged. For example, in the United Kingdom, civil society organisations critique media and political portrayals—particularly those targeting men—and underscore the socially constructed nature of these representations (Piemontese, 2025). In Poland, civil society plays a pivotal role in exposing systemic racialisation and the differential treatment of Ukrainian versus non-Ukrainian migrants (Homel-Ficenes & Grzymała-Każłowska, 2025). In Germany, civil society narratives offer a stark contrast to dominant portrayals, engaging with minoritised religious identities through frameworks of solidarity and shared humanity (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025c). Similarly, in Italy, civil society discourses are more likely than media to acknowledge the national origins of caregivers and agricultural labourers (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025).

Civil society organisations, however, tend not to engage explicitly with the racialised foundations of migration governance, reflecting broader societal tendencies to silence or marginalise discussions of race, even when racialisation is clearly operative. Nonetheless, organisations in all countries do challenge dehumanisation and racialised silencing (both central to racialisation narratives) by narratively restoring agency to migrants. A common trend in Germany and the Netherlands is emphasising migrants lived experiences (Hajer, 2024; Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025c). Despite the risk of reinforcing paternalistic representations, particularly of women and children, this approach fosters empathy and visibility. In Italy, one noteworthy example shifts focus on collective organising among racially minoritised agricultural workers, foregrounding migrant agency in contrast with dominant media and political discourses that frame

migrants through vulnerability and dependency (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025). In Poland and Finland, civil society actors focus on institutional violence (e.g., pushbacks, violations of asylum procedures), human rights, and access to services, exposing structural exclusion (Homel-Ficenes & Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025; Merikoski, 2025).

4.4. Racialisation without Race: Proxy Mechanisms in European Migration Narratives

This analysis shows how, across European contexts, moral hierarchies of deservingness often use race categories as an ordering principle to construct images of deserving or desirable migrants, as well as their counter-image. Because race itself is seldom overtly named, it operates primarily through the production of racialised social imaginaries that are shaped by colonial legacies and entrenched racist tropes. It is thus mediated and made operative through narrative devices that allow racialisation to function without being explicitly stated. These proxies vary across national contexts, reflecting specific historical, cultural, and political conditions, yet they share a common function in shaping public perceptions and policy responses.

In the United Kingdom, gendered stereotypes serve as a key proxy. Civil society and media narratives often juxtapose undeserving criminalised men with deserving victimised women (Piemontese, 2025). These figures are represented as ethnically diverse, aligning with the UK's self-image as a superdiverse and post-racial society. Yet their representation is deeply embedded in racialised assumptions about threat and vulnerability.

In Poland, racialisation is structured around cultural proximity to national identity. A clear divide emerges between Ukrainian migrants, who are perceived as geographically, culturally, linguistically and racially proximate, and non-European others, who are positioned as culturally and religiously distant and less deserving (Homel-Ficenes & Grzymała-Kazłowska, 2025). Here, race is refracted through the lens of national belonging and geopolitical alignment.

In Germany, where overt nationalism remains politically sensitive, religion becomes the dominant proxy. The Islam vs Christianity dichotomy is mobilised to construct moral hierarchies, with Muslim men often portrayed as threatening and incompatible with German values, while Ukrainian women are framed as vulnerable and deserving (Rheindorf & Vollmer, 2025c). Although religion appears more abstract and neutral, it reproduces similar racialised and gendered divisions.

The Netherlands presents a comparable dynamic, though the emphasis shifts from religion to cultural norms and behavioural expectations. The negative counter-image to the deserving Ukrainian migrant is constructed around North African national identities, with racialisation operating through narratives of rule-breaking and manipulation of the asylum system (Hajer, 2024). Here, the infringement of social norms becomes a key proxy for racial difference.

In Finland, a similar racialised hierarchy (Ukrainians vs Middle Eastern migrants) is evident, though no single proxy dominates. Instead, perceptions of threat are shaped by gendered depersonalisation and cultural affinity. The perceived distance from the migration phenomenon itself plays a critical role: migration happening in more distant regions is often framed in humanitarian terms, while mobility at Finnish borders elicits suspicion, even if protagonists are the same (Merikoski, 2025). This reflects both Finland's traditionally peripheral role in European migration trajectories and governance and its geopolitical position as the EU's largest external land border with Russia.

Finally, Italy diverges somewhat from the binary logic found in other countries. While it does not produce a rigid dichotomy between “good” and “bad” migrants, racialisation still operates through subtler proxies, including the victimisation of irregular migrants and the framing of mobility as originating from the southern shores of the Mediterranean (Garofalo Geymonat, 2025). This is shaped in part by Italy’s comparatively permissive attitude toward irregular work, and by a politicised focus on prosecuting so-called smugglers. In both cases, these dynamics evoke racialised imaginaries without explicitly naming race, reinforcing perceptions of threat and disorder.

4.5. Cross-cutting Themes

A number of cross-cutting themes emerge across the six countries. First, racialisation is predominantly implicit, operating through proxies such as nationality, religion, and gender. This allows public discourse to maintain a veneer of neutrality while reproducing exclusionary logics. Second, a racialised hierarchy of deservingness is evident in all contexts, with migrants perceived as culturally proximate (e.g., Ukrainians, Eastern European women) framed as deserving, and those from the Global South constructed as threats or burdens. Third, the dehumanisation of migrants through quantitative and impersonal language is widespread, contributing to their representation as faceless masses rather than individuals with rights and agency.

At the same time, important divergences exist. Italy stands out for its focus on labour and exploitation, with race-talk largely absent due to the universalistic orientation of workers’ organisations. In contrast, Poland and Finland exhibit more explicit racialisation, particularly in relation to geopolitical threats and national identity. Germany and the Netherlands rely heavily on religious and behavioural markers, while the UK combines moral and economic framings with gendered and ethno-national stereotypes. While the language of race may be muted or indirect, its effects are deep, structuring who is seen as deserving of rights, protection and dignity, and who is not.

5. Race and Racialisation in Public Perceptions of Irregular Migrants

Public understandings of irregular migration across Europe reveal clear patterns in how people imagine irregularity and evaluate irregularised migrants. The I-CLAIM survey shows that respondents tend to associate irregularity primarily with border crossings and asylum claims, while overlooking less visible but common pathways tied to work and everyday administrative processes. These assumptions also shape attitudes toward migrants in concrete scenarios: hiring preferences and evaluations of integration are strongly influenced by national origin, with profiles associated with racialised or non-European backgrounds consistently evaluated more negatively (see, for example, Lessard-Phillips et al., 2025; Lessard-Phillips & Sigona, 2025). Together, these trends highlight how public perceptions of irregular migration are structured by partial knowledge and racialised hierarchies that cut across countries.

5.1. Scenarios Leading to Irregularity

One of the aims of the survey was to gauge public knowledge of “irregular migration”, a term that, as we have seen from the previous section, does not consistently appear in public narratives. Respondents were asked to evaluate a series of scenarios and indicate how likely they believed each scenario was to result in irregularity. Each respondent was randomly presented with the following options: (1) someone with an expired student visa; (2) someone crossing a border without proper documentation; (3) someone waiting to

hear back from their asylum claim; (4) someone born to parents who do not have legal residence status; (5) someone hired through a recruitment company; (6) someone from the EU/UK in-between contracts.³ Respondents were then asked to answer how often they thought these scenarios would lead to irregularity (e.g., “all of the time”; “most of the time”; “sometimes”; “never”; “don’t know”).

As shown in Figure 1, respondents across all countries most frequently associated irregularity with scenarios involving border crossings and asylum claims. Because these situations align with the racialised narratives of external threat emerging from the analysis of public narratives discussed before, the public tends to view them as obvious indicators of irregularity. By contrast, one of the scenarios least linked to irregularity by respondents in all I-CLAIM countries, referred to EU migrant workers, despite this being a well-documented route into irregularity.

Figure 1 Scenarios and their link to irregularity in the I-CLAIM countries. Source: I-CLAIM survey (2025)

5.2. Hiring Preferences and Perceptions of Integration

Public perceptions toward irregular migration were measured through the use of survey experiments designed to capture respondents’ hiring preferences towards irregularised migrants—a behaviour that can be risky or illegal behaviour—and their evaluation of the level of integration of specific profiles of these migrants. The experiments were intentionally designed with a racialised dimension through the inclusion of national origins operating as a proxy for race. The sections below highlight the main ways in which these national origins mattered for overall perceptions, as well as preference for respondents based on their gender, age group, and party affiliation.

Hiring preferences

In the hiring preference experiment, respondents were randomly asked to read the profile of two hypothetical candidates for a caring role (once for a pair of male applicants, once for a pair of female

³ A UK worker in EU countries, and an EU worker in the UK.

applicants). Each candidate had a set of attributes, including a country of origin and a name. Respondents were asked to indicate the likelihood of hiring either candidate, and select who they would ultimately.

In Finland candidates from Iraq and Somalia (especially men) were less likely to be hired than Ukrainian candidates. Preference for Ukrainian profiles were positive across gender, age, and party affiliation of respondents, with right-leaning voters showing even stronger preferences for them. Negatived preferences for candidates from Iraq and Somalia were more pronounced among older respondents and right-leaning voters.

In Germany, candidates from Turkey and Syria (especially men) were less likely to be selected than those from Ukraine. Ukrainian candidates received higher preferences across genders and older age groups, as well as among Social Democratic Party (SPD) and “other” voters, the latter including far-right leaning parties. Older age groups, as well as SPD and “other” voters expressed negative preferences for the Turkish candidate, as did both men and women, older respondents, and CDU.

In Italy, candidates from Morocco (and especially male profiles) were less likely to be hired than Ukrainian candidates. Who were also viewed more favourably by respondents voting for right-wing government party *Fratelli d'Italia*. Negative preferences for Moroccan candidates appeared among men, women, middle-aged respondents, as well as supporters of *Movimento 5 Stelle*, *Fratelli d'Italia*, and non-voters. Profiles showing Peruvian candidates were viewed positively by women, middle-aged respondents, and non-voters.

In the Netherlands, candidates from Morocco (and especially male profiles) were less likely to be chosen compared to Brazilian candidates. Brazilian profiles received positive preferences from men, middle-aged adults, and supporters of the *Nieuw Sociaal Contract* (NSC) Christian-democratic party. Negative preferences for the Moroccan candidate were stronger among older age groups as well as far-right voters of *Partij voor de Vrijheid* (PVV). Filipino profiles were positively evaluated, especially among older respondents, as well as PVV and centre-right *Volkspartij voor Vrijheid en Democratie* (VVD) voters.

In Poland, candidates from Uzbekistan were less likely to be chosen than Ukrainian candidates. Positive preferences were expressed Ukrainian profiles especially among male respondents, while Filipino profiles were preferred by female respondents.

In the United Kingdom, candidates from Bangladesh (especially men) and Nigeria were less likely to be hired compared to those from Moldova, who received positive preferences across gender and voters of major parties, as well as among 40+ adults. Negative preferences for Bangladeshi profiles were found among male respondents and right-wing Reform UK voters, while Nigerian candidates were similarly viewed negatively, especially by men, 40+ adults, and voters from Conservative, Liberal Democrats, and Reform UK parties.

Assessing integration

As part of the survey, we examined how respondents assessed the “integration” of irregularised migrants. Respondents were asked to read a profile describing a hypothetical irregular migrant, including various attributes such as the country of origin, and to rate the individual’s perceived level of integration from 0 (low) to 10 (high). Each respondent evaluated two profiles.

In Finland, respondents assessed profiles from Turkey and Nigeria. While overall differences by origin were small, single Turkish men were perceived as slightly less well integrated. Female respondents viewed both origins as better integrated than male respondents did, and younger respondents gave higher integration ratings to the Turkish profile. In terms of party affiliation, voters for the True Finns (*Perussuomalaiset*) tended to give lower integration scores to both origins, whereas SPD voters were more positive in their assessments.

In Germany, respondents assessed profiles from Morocco and Moldova. Overall, Moldovan candidates were seen as better integrated than those from Morocco. Younger respondents gave higher integration ratings to both profiles. Green Party voters viewed both origins as relatively well integrated, while SPD voters were particularly positive in their assessments of the Moldovan profile.

In Italy, respondents evaluated profiles from Senegal and Moldova. Although differences by origin were limited, both men and women tended to view the Moldovan profile as better integrated, and women also gave higher integration ratings to the Senegalese profile. Younger respondents rated both profiles positively in terms of integration. *Fratelli d'Italia* voters gave lower integration scores to both origins, while voters of other parties were more positive toward the Moldovan profile. *Partito Democratico* voters and non-voters also rated the Senegalese profile as relatively well integrated.

In the Netherlands, respondents evaluated profiles from Gambia and Indonesia. Indonesian candidates were viewed as better integrated, although both profiles generally received positive integration ratings. The main exception was among far-right PVV voters, who were less positive than other respondents in their assessments of integration for both profiles.

In Poland, respondents compared profiles from Ukraine and India. No clear differences emerged in how integrated the two profiles were perceived to be, although the Indian profile received slightly lower ratings on some other characteristics, without reaching statistical significance. There were no major differences across respondent groups in how they judged integration.

In the United Kingdom, respondents were shown profiles from Kosovo and Nigeria. Male respondents gave lower integration ratings to both origins, and adult respondents (40+) also viewed both profiles as less integrated, with the most negative assessments among those aged 65 and over. In terms of party affiliation, Conservative and Reform UK voters similarly rated both profiles as less well integrated.

6. Racial Discrimination and Racialised Segmentation in Migrant Work

Examining the participation of irregularised migrant workers in specific labour-market sectors offers a strong empirical basis for understanding how racial and ethnic discrimination combines with immigration status to shape the everyday working and living conditions of migrant workers and their families. Building on the patterns observed in the previous sections, looking at the participation of irregularised migrant workers in specific labour-market sectors provides a complementary empirical lens to understand the racial logics of irregular migration in Europe.

Agriculture, domestic work, and food delivery differ significantly in public visibility, state regulation, and perceived socio-economic positioning. Yet they share important features: they are labour-intensive, marked by various degrees of informality, and heavily reliant on migrant labour. These characteristics made them a perfect fit for research such as I-CLAIM, which explores how immigration status intersects with racialised

migrant work. While the centrality of migrants in these sectors is not new, in recent years their presence has become more salient due to demographic changes, labour shortages, and the increasing reliance of European economies on temporary, circular, and irregularised forms of migration.

6.1. Agriculture

In Finland, Germany, Italy, and Poland, agriculture is a sector where the reliance on migrant labour intersects with systems of racial and ethnic differentiation that shape the allocation of work, access to rights, and experiences of exploitation. Employers, intermediaries actively draw on nationality, immigration status, perceived cultural proximity and racial difference to construct hierarchies of workers, segment tasks, and justify unequal treatment and retribution. While these practices vary across local contexts, they collectively reveal a patterned regime of racialised discrimination within the European agricultural sector that shape worker's access to rights, conditions of exploitation, and experiences social and spatial segregation.

In southern Italy (Palumbo, 2025) access to agricultural work is filtered through informal recruitment and reputational networks where national origin operates as a practical criterion for selection and assignment. African migrants are steered towards the hardest, lowest-paid, and least regulated jobs, while Eastern European women are concentrated in seasonal picking and household-adjacent roles but seldom progress to supervisory positions. Everyday bordering practices (e.g. ID checks, police patrols, and fear of denunciation) limit mobility between jobs and deter complaints, reinforcing employer discretion. The result is a segmented market in which racially minoritised workers accept inferior terms to maintain access to any employment, and informality persists even among those with valid documents because “migrant labour” is treated as inherently disposable.

The German case (Salamena, 2025b) reveals similar logics within a formally legal hiring regime. On large farms, workers are ranked by nationality and ethnicity: Polish workers are framed as the “most reliable”, ethnic Romanians (non-Roma) as acceptable but less trustworthy, while Romanian Roma are deemed undesirable. Those lower in the hierarchy receive more physically demanding work, inferior accommodation and closer supervision, with little opportunity to move into better-paid roles such as driving or packing. This stratification is sustained by the organisational infrastructure of recruitment: intermediaries controlling transport, housing and pay; on-site “trusted” workers mediating between management and crews; and disciplinary practices exploiting the ease with which seasonal employees can be replaced. Even though most workers are EU citizens and formally employed, the interaction of ethnic ranking and contractual dependence normalises differential treatment and discourages claims.

In Finland (Merikoski & Näre, 2025b), a more regulated framework still channels racialised segmentation. Sub-sectors most reliant on manual picking, such as berries and greenhouse vegetables, have been structurally “migrantised”, with recruitment pipelines oriented to specific nationalities. Thai and Ukrainian workers are repeatedly described by employers and intermediaries as disciplined, predictable and “easy to manage”, and the seasonal-work-permit system is routinised around these assumptions. By contrast, migrants from African and Middle-Eastern countries encounter barriers to recruitment and sponsorship. The single-employer permit and dependence on brokers create significant dependency even in formally regular jobs, shifting costs and risks onto migrants while limiting exit options. In practice, national-origin preferences and permit-tied dependency stabilise a racialised floor of pay and conditions for non-EU workers.

In Poland (Matuszczyk, 2025), where the agricultural workforce is overwhelmingly Ukrainian, racialisation operates through a politics of cultural proximity. Employers present Ukrainians as both “natural” and desirable: they are “like us”—a framing that translates into preferential hiring and trust within orchards and packing facilities. The temporary-protection scheme following 2022 Russia’s invasion of Ukraine widened access and legitimacy for displaced Ukrainians, while seasonal-permit workers remained more precarious, producing status hierarchies within the same nationality. The result is a demand structure that produces hierarchies within Ukrainian migrants, shaping bargaining power and job security. Across these contexts, employers and intermediaries transform perceptions of nationality and “fit” into structural dependence through legal and organisational devices. Seasonal permits, employer-linkage, and subcontracting formalise the unequal treatment originally justified by cultural stereotypes. Workers who are deemed reliable or compliant are channelled into repetitive, low-wage roles; those seen as unfamiliar or politically risky are excluded altogether. Workers’ dependency on their employers and intermediaries is produced and maintained through systems that make it difficult for workers to negotiate better conditions or leave exploitative situations: accommodation tied to employment, debt to recruiters, and the constant threat of replacement. These mechanisms make discrimination appear functional and legitimate within local labour systems.

Comparatively, the four studies expose a shared grammar of racialised sorting in agricultural labour markets. Employers and intermediaries translate perceived cultural traits, such as reliability, discipline, and fit, into concrete allocations of job roles, wage levels and career ceilings. Legal and administrative frameworks then convert these perceptions into enduring structures of dependency. Whether employment is informal, as in many Italian settings, or formally regular, as in Germany and Finland, race and nationality function as proxies for compliance and replaceability.

Worker dependency emerges as a central issue across all contexts, shaped by national institutional environments that racialise labour in distinct yet comparable ways. In Italy, it is intensified by irregular immigration status and street-level policing, which amplify employer leverage and suppress collective mobilisation. In Germany, ethnic hierarchies persist even among EU citizens through subtle gradations of “whiteness” and cultural proximity—Poles over Romanians, Roma at the bottom—revealing that racialisation operates within as well as beyond immigration status. In Finland, formalised recruitment and visa systems institutionalise segmentation under the guise of administrative neutrality. In Poland, preferential hiring of Ukrainians consolidates imagined ethnic homogeneity while excluding visibly racialised non-Europeans, embedding ethno-national preference in everyday practice. These national regimes—whether informal, bureaucratic, or framed by EU mobility—embed racialised assumptions into legal and organisational structures. Across all cases, being from a favoured origin does not remove dependency, and holding documents does not eliminate racialised assumptions that restrict advancement. At best, administrative status functions as an additional form of capital useful to access slightly better working and living conditions.

6.2. Domestic Work

Across Finland, Italy, the Netherlands, and the United Kingdom, domestic work remains one of the most precarious sectors of the labour market. While the legal and policy frameworks differ sharply across these countries, underlying processes of racialisation consistently structure who enters this work, how the sector is organised, and what forms of protection or exploitation are available. Immigration status and gender intersect with race and nationality to produce a continuum of dependency that spans formal and informal employment.

Racialised segmentation structures domestic work from the initial point of recruitment and is reinforced by legal frameworks that regulate migrant access to employment and rights. Across Italy, Finland, the Netherlands and the United Kingdom, entry into the sector is shaped by a double filtering process: bureaucratic such as visas and work permits, and cultural logics rooted in employer preferences and ethnic stereotypes. Together, these filters the conditions migrants access to employment, embedding racialised assumptions into the organisation of the sector from the outset and reinforcing patterns of exclusion and dependency.

In Italy (Marchetti & Lashchuk, 2025), hiring occurs almost entirely through informal networks where nationality, language and reputation determine access to jobs. These initial filters shape who enters the sector and under what conditions. Eastern European women, particularly Ukrainians and Moldovans, dominate the live-in elder-care sector and are valued for perceived cultural proximity and linguistic adaptability. In contrast, African and Asian women face narrower options and greater suspicion and are often excluded from more desirable roles. Administrative status does not necessarily improve prospects: even women with residence permits are hired informally and remain outside social protection. This segmentation at the point of entry translates into exploitative working conditions, with wages often falling below the legal minimum and unpaid standby time being common. Employers justify such conditions through moral discourses of “help” and “sacrifice”, while bureaucratic hurdles make formalisation difficult even for documented migrants, reinforcing dependency and exclusion throughout the employment trajectory.

In the Netherlands (Hajer & van Liempt, 2025), entry into domestic work is shaped by the *Regeling Dienstverlening aan Huis*, the Home Services Regulation, which exempts households from standard employer and effectively legalises informality. This deregulated framework creates a deregulated zone in which trust replaces formal contracts, and workers are recruited primarily through co-ethnic referral chains, especially among Brazilian, Filipino, and Indonesian migrants. While these networks provide limited protection, they also reinforce segmentation by nationality, confining workers within particular ethnic niches and informal arrangements. At the same time, the lack of formal contracts leaves workers vulnerable: those who ask for written contracts or benefits are easily replaced, and inspection authorities have limited jurisdiction inside private homes. As a result, the combination of legal exemptions and informal recruitment normalises insecurity and restricts access to rights.

In the United Kingdom (Sigona, Piemontese, Mendes, et al., 2025), entry into domestic work is increasingly shaped by the broader tightening of immigration enforcement, with sponsorship dependence emerging as the main vector of vulnerability. Workers’ right to stay is contingent on an employer’s compliance yet sponsors frequently breach contract terms or underpay without consequence. When a sponsor loses a licence or fails to renew a certificate, the worker instantly falls into irregularity, losing both income and, in case of live-in working arrangements, accommodation. This framework directly shapes working conditions: migrants are often subject to wage deductions, unpaid overtime, and threats of Home Office reporting. The sponsorship and enforcement regimes create a system in which administrative status becomes the primary instrument of labour discipline. Workers risk deportation if they report exploitation or change employer, while irregular migrants fear exposure through wage claims or tax records. In the UK context, the legal framework not only regulates access to employment but also institutionalise insecurity and racialised control over migrant labour.

In Finland (Merikoski & Näre, 2025a), recruitment occurs through agencies or word-of-mouth but remains strongly stratified by nationality. Migrants from the Philippines, Africa, and South Asia dominate private cleaning, often working for subcontractors or directly for households. These recruitment channels, combined with restrictive regularisation policies and an employer-linked permit system maintain workers’

dependence and limit bargaining power. This segmentation at the point of entry directly influences working conditions: household cleaning remains largely beyond labour inspection, and workers without stable permits are excluded from social insurance. Agency-mediated workers frequently report unpaid overtime and deductions that go unchallenged for fear of job loss.

Across these contexts, the ability of migrant workers to claim rights or improve conditions is consistently constrained by the convergence of informality, immigration control, and weak labour enforcement. Entry into domestic work often occurs through precarious legal channels or informal networks, setting the stage for ongoing vulnerability. Job loss or administrative change often reproduces irregularity rather than resolving it, leading to loss of income, accommodation, and administrative status, leaving migrants dependent on co-ethnic referrals for survival. While formal rights may exist on paper, they are structurally inaccessible. The result is a continuum of insecurity in which racialised migrants sustain indispensable care and cleaning work under conditions of perpetual contingency.

Crucially, the convergence of racialisation and legal status is reproduced not only through employment structures but also through the management of intimacy within the workplace. Whether in live-in arrangements or outsourced cleaning services, employers deploy narratives of trust, care, and cultural stereotypes to justify control and surveillance. Migrant workers are often expected to be invisible, compliant, and grateful, while any assertion of rights is framed as a breach of moral or emotional contracts. These dynamics vary in form, ranging from paternalistic oversight in live-in care to selective trust in outsourced cleaning, but they share a common logic: the domestic sphere is not merely a site of employment, but it operates as a regime of governance where racialised assumptions shape a division of labour that naturalises unequal treatment and precludes contestation.

The four country studies converge on a shared pattern: domestic work in Europe operates through the racialisation of intimacy. Employers' perceptions of national character and cultural proximity determine who is considered trustworthy enough to enter private homes and who is restricted to the hardest, least visible tasks. Immigration rules—whether Italy's fragmented amnesty system, the Netherlands' deregulated Home Service Regulation, the UK's sponsorship regime, or Finland's employer-tied permits—translate these perceptions into durable dependence. Racial and ethnic discrimination in domestic work is systemic rather than incidental. It is sustained by the intersection of private household organisation, immigration governance, and persistent gendered assumptions about care. The home thus emerges as a key site in which Europe's racialised migration regimes are reproduced on an everyday scale.

6.3. Food Delivery

Food delivery is one of the most dynamic and publicly visible segments of migrant labour in Europe. Research conducted in Germany, the Netherlands, Poland and the United Kingdom reveal how distinct configurations of irregularity emerge at the intersection of immigration regimes, digital management systems, and racialised labour hierarchies. By focusing on specific urban settings (Berlin, Utrecht, Warsaw, and Birmingham), our research illuminates the racialised infrastructure underpinning the sector. First, it shows how food delivery attracts migrants with precarious administrative and social status, particularly newcomers, making it a highly migrantised field in which workers from minority ethnic background are strongly represented. Second, our research highlights how the sector's digital infrastructure not only facilitates algorithmic control and customer evaluation, which disproportionately penalise racially minoritised individuals and those with fewer resources and greater dependency on informal networks, but

is also increasingly linked to immigration enforcement. Third, racial profiling in public space (through ID checks, surveillance, and differential policing) further exposes racially minoritised migrant riders to everyday bordering practices, reinforcing their vulnerability and exclusion.

Across the four contexts, delivery work attracts migrants who occupy unstable administrative and social positions—students, asylum seekers, overstayers, and workers awaiting status decisions. Yet, the sector's apparent low entry barriers conceal multiple layers of dependency created by subcontracting, account-sharing, and the digital mediation of employment: recruitment, and in some cases access to borrowed or rented 'substitute' accounts, often occurs through informal channels such as WhatsApp groups, co-ethnic referrals, and student networks, and is shaped by visa restrictions and employer-linked permits. In Berlin, international students working as delivery riders exceed permitted working hours to meet living costs (Salamena, 2025a); in Utrecht and Warsaw, non-EU migrants rely on fleet operators or intermediary companies that shift legal and financial responsibilities onto them (Homel & Grzymala-Kazłowska, 2025; van Liempt & Hajer, 2025); in Birmingham, delivery riders from different national backgrounds combine self-employment with informal account sharing (Sigona, Piemontese, Achi, et al., 2025). These arrangements offer income but no protection. Moreover, loss or expiry of visas frequently pushes riders into irregular status without interrupting their participation in the platform economy. Across all contexts, deteriorating working conditions made the sector attractive to migrant newcomers with fewer resources who would otherwise be excluded from formal employment, embedding administrative status, nationality, and race into the very structure of labour supply.

Although marketed as flexible and autonomous, delivery work is tightly governed by digital infrastructures that not only determine access to shifts, allocate tasks, and monitor performance, but also reproduce racialised inequalities. Algorithmic systems allocate shifts, monitor performance, and rate workers based on speed, reliability, and customer feedback. These metrics disproportionately penalise workers who depend on "substitute" accounts or lack resources to access faster e-bikes or mopeds due to their precarious residence status. Yet, as the Dutch case demonstrates, they also penalise racially minoritised individuals through customer ratings that reflect social biases related to accent, appearance, and perceived cultural proximity, into digital hierarchies, influencing access to profitable routes (van Liempt & Hajer, 2025). In the UK, digital identity verification is increasingly tied to immigration enforcement, illustrating how platform governance and algorithmic bordering are becoming intertwined, profoundly exacerbating existing racial hierarchies (Sigona, Piemontese, Achi, et al., 2025). In contexts where access to the sector depends more on subcontracting by agencies, like in Germany and Poland, migrants sign contracts with fleet managers rather than platforms and the processes of racial exclusion take another form (Homel & Grzymala-Kazłowska, 2025; Salamena, 2025a). Subcontracting creates chains of dependence in which pay, hours and equipment provision vary by nationality and perceived reliability. Non-European riders, particularly those racially minoritised or limited local language skills, are concentrated in the least stable and profitable arrangements. These systems transform administrative uncertainty into a managerial resource, making racialised migrants more disposable and replaceable while denying them visibility as rights-bearing workers.

Because delivery work unfolds in public space, visibility itself becomes a key vector of racialised control. Black and Asian riders in Birmingham, Berlin, and Warsaw report frequent ID checks, police harassment, and immigration enforcement actions—something Ukrainian couriers in Warsaw do not encounter because they are generally perceived as "familiar" and subject to fewer controls. Such everyday bordering practices map national hierarchies onto urban mobility, rendering the city a space where race and legality are continually

policed. Riders face not only economic precarity but also the constant threat of surveillance and detention. Public space thus becomes a terrain where racial profiling, immigration control, and labour discipline converge, reinforcing the marginalisation of racially minoritised migrants in the platform economy.

6.4. Cross-sectoral analysis

Across agriculture, domestic work, and food delivery, the I-CLAIM studies show that race and ethno-national identities remain central to the organisation of migrant labour in Europe, though they operate through distinct sectoral logics. In agriculture, racialisation functions through segmentation, ranking workers by nationality and perceived proximity to the national majority. In domestic work, it operates through intimacy, shaping who is deemed trustworthy to enter private homes and legitimising asymmetrical relations of care. In food delivery, it unfolds through visibility, where digital infrastructures and public space turn racialised bodies into objects of surveillance and regulation.

Across these settings, immigration control interacts with labour regimes to transform legal status into a mechanism of racial ordering. Irregularity is best understood as a relational position, produced through the interplay of race, bureaucracy, and work. This relationality embeds existing racial hierarchies within systems of employment and migration, such that even legally secure, racialised EU minorities may encounter forms of devaluation and exclusion akin to those faced by precarious migrant workers. What changes is not the underlying mechanism of racialisation but the institutional form it takes. Together, these findings expose how Europe's dependence on migrant labour is sustained by racialised regimes of flexibility and control.

7. Conclusions

The comparative findings across six European countries show that racial logics are central to the production and governance of irregular migration. Irregularity is not a neutral legal status but a racialised position produced and maintained through systems that differentially value human mobility and labour. Legal frameworks, administrative practices, public narratives, and labour regimes together form a racialised infrastructure of control that organises inclusion and exclusion.

Racism operates as a *hidden infrastructure* built into the architecture of migration, labour, and welfare systems rather than expressed through overt hostility. Bureaucratic discretion, visa dependency, and conditional access to welfare transform administrative procedures into instruments of racialised control. Political and media narratives construct hierarchies of worth through proxies such as religion, nationality, and culture, legitimising exclusion under the guise of neutrality. The recurrent contrast between “deserving” refugees, such as Ukrainians, and “undeserving” irregular migrants from the Global South exemplifies how moral hierarchies sustain Europe's migration regimes. In the labour market, racial and legal hierarchies convert precarity into economic advantage: employers and intermediaries exploit nationality and perceived cultural traits as practical tools for sorting workers, while immigration control transforms these perceptions into binding dependency.

The report further shows that these mechanisms do not only affect migrants with insecure status. Racialised EU minorities, particularly Roma communities, are also subjected to forms of surveillance, exclusion, and devaluation that mirror those directed at irregular migrants. They are frequently treated as *quasi-foreigners* within their own European Union, illustrating how racism blurs the boundaries between legality and

illegality, legal residence and exclusion. This continuum reveals that irregularity is not simply a matter of legal status but a racialised condition produced through the governance of difference.

Recognising racism as infrastructural has far-reaching implications. Tackling irregularity requires more than administrative reform—it demands rethinking equality, rights, and belonging. This includes extending anti-discrimination frameworks to cover immigration and residence status; decoupling access to welfare and public services from legal residence; strengthening labour inspection and union access in migrant-dominated sectors; and supporting civil-society initiatives that centre racial justice and migrant agency.

These findings speak directly to the ambitions of the EU Anti-Racism Strategy 2026–2030. They suggest that without confronting migration governance as a racialising infrastructure, efforts to mainstream anti-racism risk leaving untouched the institutional mechanisms through which racialised irregularity is produced and maintained.

Europe's irregularity regime is not simply a question of border management or labour regulation. It is a racialised system that differentiates lives, reproduces inequality, and constrains solidarity. Confronting it requires addressing the deep historical and institutional roots of racialisation within European governance. Doing so is not only a matter of justice for migrants and racialised minorities—it is essential to the renewal of European democracy itself.

References

- Carrera, S., & Colombi, D. (2025). *Irregularising Human Mobility: EU Migration Policies and the European Commission's Role*. Springer Nature Switzerland. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-74021-3>
- Garofalo Geymonat, G. (2025). *The public discourse on migration, irregularity and work in Italy. The intersectionality of narratives in media, civil society and politics*. I-CLAIM Project.
- Hajer, M. (2024). *Discourses about irregularised migrants in the Netherlands. Representation and narratives in media, politics, and civil society*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/15094196>
- Hajer, M., & van Liempt, I. (2025). *Irregular migrants in the Dutch Domestic Work Sector*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775196>
- Hajer, M., Vasileiadi, C., & van Liempt, I. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity: The Netherlands*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/10977067>
- Homel, K., & Grzymala-Kazłowska, A. (2025). *Living and working conditions of migrants in the delivery sector in Poland*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15780657>
- Homel-Ficenes, K., & Grzymała-Kazłowska, A. (2025). *Narratives about irregularised migrants in Poland. Mass-media, politics and social organisations*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15094139>
- Lessard-Phillips, L., Hajer, M., & Van Liempt, I. (2025). *Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in Netherlands*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/17948443>
- Lessard-Phillips, L., & Sigona, N. (2025). *Public understanding and attitudes to irregular migration in the UK*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/17867965>
- Marchetti, S., & Lashchuk, I. (2025). *Irregularised migrant domestic workers in Naples, Italy*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775615>
- Matuszczyk, K. (2025). *Migrant labour in the Polish agriculture sector*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15780736>
- Matuszczyk, K., Grzymala-Kazłowska, A., & Homel, K. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity: Poland*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.11094089>
- Merikoski, P. (2025). *Narratives of Irregular Migration in Finland*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/15094303>
- Merikoski, P., & Näre, L. (2025a). *Precarious migrants in domestic cleaning work. Findings from Finland*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775520>
- Merikoski, P., & Näre, L. (2025b). *Precurity and informality in agricultural food production in Finland: The role of migrant workers*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775571>
- Merikoski, P., Näre, L., & Karti, S.-M. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity: Finland*. I-CLAIM Project. [10.5281/zenodo.11066290](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11066290)
- Näre, L., Palumbo, L., Merikoski, P., & Marchetti, S. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Migrant Irregularity: Comparative Report*. I-CLAIM. <https://doi.org/10.5281/ZENODO.12564072>
- Palumbo, L. (2025). *Women migrant workers with precarious legal status in the agricultural sector in Southern Italy*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15833920>

- Palumbo, L., & Marchetti, S. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructures of Irregularity: Italy*. I-CLAIM Project. 10.5281/zenodo.11208939
- Piemontese, S. (2025). *The narrative construction of migrant irregularity in the United Kingdom. Representation and narratives in media, politics, and civil society*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111611>
- Piemontese, S., & Sigona, N. (2024). *The legal and policy infrastructure of irregularity: United Kingdom*. I-CLAIM Project. 10.5281/zenodo.10966184
- Rheindorf, M., & Vollmer, B. (2025a). *Discourses about irregularised migrants: Representation and narratives in media, politics, and civil society in Europe. Comparative Report*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15115331>
- Rheindorf, M., & Vollmer, B. (2025b). *Methodological Note: Corpus-based discourse analysis of migration-related discourses in media, politics and civil society*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://zenodo.org/records/15094216>
- Rheindorf, M., & Vollmer, B. A. (2025c). *Discourses about irregularised migrants in Germany*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15111751>
- Rheindorf, M., Vollmer, B., & Liebsch, M. (2024). *The Legal and Policy Infrastructure of Irregularity: Germany*. I-CLAIM Project. 10.5281/zenodo.11109546
- Salamena, B. B. (2025a). *Irregularised migrants in the Delivery Sector (Berlin)*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775449>
- Salamena, B. B. (2025b). *Living and Working Conditions of migrant seasonal workers in agriculture in Germany*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775486>
- Sigona, N., Piemontese, S., Achi, A., & Mendes, S. S. (2025). *Irregularised migrant workers in the UK food delivery sector*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775291>
- Sigona, N., Piemontese, S., Mendes, S. S., & Achi, A. (2025). *Irregularised migrants doing domestic work in the UK*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775346>
- Sigona, N., & van Liempt, I. (2025). *The irregularisation of migration and migrants' irregular condition: An assemblage perspective* (No. 50). Institute for Research into International Migration and Superdiversity. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17489274>
- van Liempt, I., & Hajer, M. (2025). *Irregular migrants and precarity in the Dutch Food Delivery*. I-CLAIM Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775098>